

Identity in Social Ritual: Tradition and Its Absence

Roger Scruton speaks on behalf of a house that survived. Yuri Lotman gathers his thoughts to draft the blueprint for a new house

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Caricature of Y. LOTMAN and R. SCRUTON. Author: I. GANPANTSURA

A person's biography and experience are a heavy and important tool; and identity, in a personal sense, is how we choose to interact with our experience and the place we occupy in life — that is, with our reality. Identity is a set of values and empirical knowledge through which we form an idea of ourselves. But we form these “ideas of ourselves” only

in comparison with others. It turns out that our identity is also our view of everything that exists.

By changing our identity, we can give ourselves another life — discarding something here, nurturing something new there...

But the liberal paradox lies in the fact that a person is deliberately offered the “freedom to choose” their identity: their roles, goals, self-awareness; whereas in reality, their identity is already a product of the system.

A Critique of Anarchic Destruction for the Sake of Creation

Pressure from one’s own biography sets the boundaries for their identity. This is where dissatisfaction with life comes from — the inability to escape the system. But we cannot destroy the system that gave us our biography; that would be too reckless. For in that case, we would have to physically exterminate one another, because each of us is a police officer of this system.

And by the way, our current freedom would also vanish. For we would lose the tradition that preserves it, and power-hungry bandits would seize their opportunity.

To morally abstract oneself from this former world is also a dubious idea. How would that help our sense of reality? After all, Freud’s categories of the “consciousness and the I” are merely the surface of the psychic apparatus. That means they are connected to the external world, where the system dominates.

Transponent Identity: Liberal

This means we must act more subtly — not by destroying or avoiding. This is the basis for a critique of anarchist ideas in the personal and psychological sense of identity.

We must begin with our inner world — within the soul, in the spiritual foundations of true tradition: family, religion, or anything that genuinely inspires a person.

But even here, the liberal myth has gone down a phantom path. It dictates: the restructuring of one's identity through external symbols of protest, which offer the illusion of a personality outside of the system.

A visible symbol of this is dyed hair — a trend of the ruling ideology disguised as protest and freedom of expression, of creativity and the inner world. The key phrase is “inner world.” People come from different nations and backgrounds; they cannot possibly have an inner world that can be painted over all at once with the same trend. The complexity of human personality, their family tradition and experience — these are not taken into account.

The Conservative Approach

“Take any aspect of the Western inheritance of which our ancestors were proud, and you will find university courses devoted to deconstructing it. Take any positive feature of our political and cultural inheritance, and you will find concerted efforts in both the

media and the academy to place it in quotation marks, and make it look like an imposture or a deceit...”

— *Sir Roger Scruton, ‘How to Be a Conservative’*

There is a striking precision to it: the modern left-liberal system integrates protest against the traditional world into mass culture. It promises the individual liberation from an allegedly imposed identity. But instead of genuine freedom, it offers only external symbols and new boundaries — presented as personal choice.

A person severed from tradition, religion, and roots does not become free — they are dragged into a race to meet new expectations: to be expressive, unique, “on trend,” progressive. Thus, authentic identity dissolves into a construction set of masks.

A conservative would propose that a person weave their identity with their own hands, using threads of personal experience and ancestral gift. In doing so, one becomes embedded in the nation and feels confident and connected. There is no longer a desire to destroy the existing socio-cultural system, because it no longer imposes itself through constraints. One can now choose which aspect to lean on: personal experience or ancestral heritage.

A mature, fully-formed individual balances between the two. Tradition becomes their moral compass, guarding them against uncritical fusion with the system. And personal experience, in interaction with the world, enriches their intellectual horizon, providing the colors with which they paint the picture of their identity.

Thus, we arrive at an example of the Western individual and their individuality, comprised of tradition and mature choice.

The Semantic Vacuum Without Tradition

The conservative approach to the question of identity is only possible in the context of deeply rooted nation-states, as Scruton describes. Where a tradition of national loyalty exists, passed down through generations, it gives rise to millions of individual family traditions. These, in contrast to personal experience, form a person's identity.

But what about, for example, Russia — where during the Soviet era it was feared, or simply frowned upon, to ask about one's ancestors or show interest in “anachronisms” like nobility — by people whose generation had already declared a break with tradition?

The state introduced a new tradition, through Vernadsky's broad project of the “Noosphere” — a vision of the supremacy of human reason over the world. Propaganda placed space exploration and a materialist worldview at the forefront. But gradually, since the Perestroika era, even this value system began to shift once again.

Yet that world, too, is fading. In a society once afraid to speak of tradition, glasnost arrives, and the new Russia demands a new project.

This can be called a true cultural revolution — for even among dissidents, a semantic vacuum emerges. There is no one left to fear, no more threats or persecutions. Their colleagues from human rights circles are now running the country.

There is no one left to sustain the old world. People are not robots; they will not build ultra-advanced rockets without an answer to the question: for whom? For communism and Vernadsky, or for Mother Russia? A semantic vacuum sets in.

A Chance for Russia — Lotman's Path

In 1988, Yuri Mikhailovich Lotman recorded a series of lectures titled *Conversations on Russian Culture*, where over the course of 32 episodes he shared the wealth of material he had studied throughout his life as a Russian intellectual. He spoke of the Russian Empire — its officials and poets, orders and warriors. He spoke of the old world convincingly and lovingly, as if telling a fairy tale. Yet he was born and lived his entire life within the Soviet project. And still, he did not speak about Vernadsky — he spoke about Pushkin.

One might imagine Lotman's identity as that of a professor from the Russian Empire. But would his lectures have been just as valuable then? After all, he would have spoken of Pushkin while living in Pushkin's world. Lotman instead reveals, in these lectures, the essence of broken continuity — he searched for himself and his identity within the Soviet system but never became part of it.

Sources of Identity:

For Scruton, identity is grounded in the cultural and moral traditions of one's ancestors, with personal experience as a particular layer. This produces a national loyalism. Lotman, in contrast, offers a different kind of identity, marked by a painful rupture of tradition and a reliance

on the sober acceptance of reality — and the founding of a new tradition through the culture of communication.

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This is the entire map of European and Russian history since the beginning of the 20th century.

The Culture of Communication — the Foundation of Lotman's Identity

The rupture of tradition is clearly illustrated in the way people address strangers. It is hard to say the ideologically charged word *comrade*, which survives only in the army or as a memory of the Soviet past. The forms *citizen* or *sir* sound overly formal — used by police and courts. In the vocabulary of post-Soviet countries, there is a lack of respectful and familiar address for initial contact.

Lotman remarked:

“One often hears such ugly, even frightening forms of address as ‘woman’ or ‘man’ — this is monstrous. It only testifies to the destruction of social ritual...”

Small groups create traditions that grow into the roots of larger societies. In a small collective, a person's identity is highly unstable, which leads them to seek emigration into Western traditionalism — or,

on the contrary, to anchor themselves through the egoism of liberal chaos, which erodes social interaction.

“There are always certain collective ‘we’ — defined through forms of address. And by the way, if we have lost common forms of address, they are not lost in small groups: in student slang, in the language of youth. Where the narrow boundaries of a group are outlined through language...”

— *Yuri Lotman*, Lecture №10. Human Communication, 1988

Lotman proposes a third path — the ethics of intellectual dignity, which evolves into the ethics of creation.

This multi-directional path is shaped by a sense of duty, liberated from the boundaries of the former tradition — at least from much of it.

It is marked by capacities that allow one to resist falling into liberal multiculturalism and the anarchy of destruction.

It is a path of constructing identity within many small groups, based on mutual recognition of the person — and thus reaffirming an active identity of the national community, the foundation of which will be these very small societies.

For if there is no tradition whose boundaries must be obeyed, one can create their own. But such an identity will not aim toward destruction — it will be directed toward creation. For at the very first stage of its emergence, it requires communication and attention to others...

“Social relations — even at the most basic level — are a subject of high culture, of cultural creation. And in this sense it is especially important to turn to the past, particularly when the times are dynamic — when everything is changing. And often, we find ourselves without the basic means to understand one another. And how important it is to understand each other — this goes without saying...”

— Lotman

It seems to me that a hermeneutic interpretation of Yuri Lotman’s work on the ethics of language and the exceptional importance of communication is essential to the foundation of a new Eastern European conservatism.

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In continuation of the author's reflections on the interaction between tradition, identity, and system...

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